

TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES AT ROOM AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

In this study Nicalon/CAS II specimens are subjected to tensile loading at room and elevated temperatures. The testing is done in situ in an SEM and the tensile damage is observed and recorded from first crack to complete failure. Using the experimental data, a stress-strain curve characterizing the tensile behavior of the CMC is constructed. To simulate and predict the observed behavior, a theoretical model based on matrix cracking and interfacial debonding is developed. It is found that there is a good qualitative and quantitative agreement between theoretical and experimental results.

Keywords: ceramic matrix composites, tensile behavior, matrix cracking, interfacial debonding, fiber bridging, fiber breakage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic materials are known to have good resistance to oxidation at high temperature and to environmental degradation in corrosive media. Thus they are very suited for use in high temperature applications. Yet their use in structural applications has been extremely limited due to their low toughness and low strength which is attributed to pores or microcracks in the material. These deficiencies are being overcome with better processing methods and by reinforcing them with ceramic fibers. The advent of ceramic matrix composites thus provides a two-fold advantage: not only the strength and fracture toughness of the material can be improved, but also the composite can be tailored to specific applications. Indeed it has been shown that, when strengthened with high strength fibers, ceramic matrix composites exhibit an increase in fracture toughness and tensile strength [1,2]. A variety of ceramic matrix composite systems have been developed for engineering applications ranging from cutting tools to aerospace structures [3,4]. Examples for ceramic matrix composite systems are C/glass [5], C/SiC [6], SiC/glass [7], SiC/LAS glass ceramic [8-12], SiC/BMAS glass-ceramic [13], SiC/Alumina [14], SiC/mullite [15], Nicalon/SiC [16].

In the aforementioned studies, experimental results on damage behavior of ceramic matrix composites were obtained by failing the specimens with either tensile or three-point bending loading at room or elevated temperature [9-12]. The aim of the present study is to observe and

record in-situ the damage behavior of Nicalon/CAS II composites at room and elevated temperatures. For this purpose, Nicalon/CAS II specimens are subjected to tensile loading and the damage is recorded from first crack to complete failure. Next an analytical model which simulates the observed behavior is developed and a theoretical stress-strain curve is generated using the finite element technique. It is found that there is good qualitative and quantitative agreement between theoretical and experimental results.

2. TESTING PROCEDURE

The experimental set-up used in this research project, as shown in Figure 1, mainly consists of a Hitachi S-2400 scanning electron microscope equipped with an E.F. Fullam tensile/heating substage. The testing facility was designed to conduct high-temperature, micromechanical tensile testing of ceramic matrix composite "dog-bone" specimens. The material tested in this study was made of Nicalon-fiber/CAS II matrix composite obtained from Corning Glass Works. Table 1 shows the thermomechanical properties of the constituents of the composite. The composite specimens had a 40% fiber volume fraction. Fibers were unidirectionally aligned along the gage-length direction. The specimens were cut from a rectangular ceramic matrix composite panel. Gage section of the specimen was machined using a Leco VC-50 Cari/Cut fine-mesh diamond saw and finished with a Dremel motorized hand-held grinder with a silicon carbide tip to ensure no fiber protrusion.

Figure 1. The experimental setup.

The central part of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 2, was directly contacted with the E.F. Fullam heating substage which is made of ceramic material. The maximum heated area of the heating substage is 0.65"x0.65". It can sustain a maximum working temperature of 1100°C and is equipped with a water-cooled heat sink for continuous operation. Temperature is measured by three platinum 30% rhodium-platinum 6% rhodium thermocouples and controlled by adjusting a variable resistor. Since the whole operation is conducted within the chamber of a scanning electron microscope (in this study a Hitachi S-2400) which is usually vacuumed at 1.5×10^{-6} Pa or better, no heat-loss will occur due to thermal convection. The specimen was first polished using fine-grade diamond paste containing 15-, 6-, and 1-micron particles until the surface was well finished and the fibers and matrix could be seen clearly under a Nikon UM-2 universal measurement microscope. The specimen was then cleaned with acetone in a Bronson ultrasonic cleaner for 10 minutes. Finally the bottom face of the specimen was coated with silver paint before it was mounted into the E.F. Fullam tensile substage. Because it is very difficult to drill holes in a ceramic composite specimen, the top and bottom parts of the specimen were mounted through stainless steel clamps with serrated teeth to the crossheads of the E.F. Fullam tensile substage. To

Figure 2. Specimen geometry.

ensure that no slipping occurred between the ceramic composite specimen and the serrated clamps during testing, cyanoacrylate-based extra-strength epoxy was also applied on the clamp-specimen interfaces. The clamped specimen was then mounted to the tensile substage and was left to cure for at least 24 hours to ensure the epoxy had hardened and was completely dry before testing.

As shown in Fig. 1, the assembly of the specimen, and the heating/ tensile substages were then placed inside the chamber of a Hitachi S-2400 SEM. By using the X-Y staging control of the scanning electron microscope, micrographical patterns within the central gage area can be observed and recorded. The tensile substage is driven by a variable-speed motor which has a maximum speed of 90 rpm. Through a gear mechanism with a 100 to 1 reduction ratio, the crosshead speed can be controlled within 0.127 mm/min (or 0.005"/min). The tensile substage can provide a tensile load of up to 455 kgs (1000 lbs). The applied load was increased gradually until the specimen failed totally. During this loading sequence, micrographs were taken to record various microcracking and damage patterns of the specimen. Since the specimen is very thin (only 1.6 mm or 0.0625"), it is expected that failure occurred through the thickness. Thus the recorded micrographs of the surface fracture represents through-the-thickness failure of the specimen. Quality of the recorded micrographs was further enhanced by an Imaging Technology Advanced Frame Grabber (AFG) digital image analyzer through contrast and edge enhancement techniques.

Table 1. Properties of Nicalon-fiber and CAS II-matrix (provided by Corning Glass Works).

	CAS II Matrix	Nicalon Fiber
Nominal Composition	CaO·Al ₂ O ₃ ·SiO ₂	Si ₃ C ₄ O
Elastic Modulus Msi(GPa)		
25°C	13.8(95)	28.3(195)
1000°C	13.5(93)	22.9(158)
1200°C	11.7(81)	22.5(155)
Thermal Expansion(10 ⁶ /°C)		
	5.0(25-1000°C)	3.1(25°C-200°C)
	-----	4.0(25°C-1000°C)
Fracture Toughness K _{IC} (MPa m ^{1/2})		
25°C	2.16±0.11	-----
1000°C	1.30±0.17	-----
Fiber/Matrix Interfacial Shear Strength		
25°C	15.7±2.0 MPa	

The tensile stage is designed in such a way that when the load increases, the top and bottom crossheads move in opposite directions to minimize the shift of the observed site. This is achieved by machining the stainless-steel loading columns into worms of reverse directions. Thus searching and refocusing the damaged zone after each load increment are very handy. The applied loads were recorded by a miniature load cell equipped with a digital readout. The relative displacement of the crossheads were measured by a high-precision, strain-gage-type extensometer which is also fitted with a digital readout. The load-displacement data were recorded and converted into a stress-strain curve. The evolution of damage recorded by micrographs were identified with the corresponding stress and strain. Finally the ruptured specimens were observed under a Nikon UM-2 universal measuring microscope for postmortem examination.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical stress-strain curve for the room-temperature, tensile damage behavior of a Nicalon/CAS II with 40% fiber volume fraction is shown in Fig. 3. Figures 4 and 5 depict the tensile-damaged stress-strain curves for two batches of specimens. As shown in Fig. 3, the tensile damage behavior of the ceramic matrix composite is characterized by a nonlinear curve made up of three sections. Upon load application, the relation between stress and strain was linear and its slope, as indicated in Fig. 3, was equivalent to the stiffness of an intact Nicalon/CAS II specimen (19.6 Msi or 135 GPa). At Point A of Fig. 3, visible matrix microcracks can be observed at a stress level between 10 to 20 ksi. Figure 6(A) shows a typical microfractograph of this point. Even though matrix cracks had formed at this stage, no significant slope change in the stress-strain curve had been recorded. A sudden slope change occurred at Point B (about 35 ksi) signaling extensive matrix cracking, as recorded in the microfractograph Fig. 6(B). Further matrix cracking was observed until the ultimate fracture load was reached at Point C. The corresponding microfractograph of Point C is shown in Fig. 6(C). During the stage from Point B to Point C matrix microcracks coalesced to form several major cracks. Although the overall stiffness of the damaged specimen was significantly lower than that of an intact specimen during the stage BC, the instantaneous stress-strain curve of this stage resembled the strain-hardening behavior of a metal under plastic deformation.

Figure 3. A typical stress-strain curve for Nicalon/CAS II in room temperature.

Figure 4. Tensile test for Nicalon/CAS II specimens (batch one).

Figure 5. Tensile tests for Nicalon/CAS II specimens (batch two).

In addition, we also observed that the crack opening displacements (i.e., the spacing between the two faces of a crack) were larger in microfractograph Fig. 6(C) than those in Fig. 6(B). This observation indicates that fiber debonding (or, equivalently, the formation of fiber-matrix interfaces) was in process. The propagation of fiber-matrix interfaces eventually lead to

the catastrophic failure of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 6(D) which corresponds to Point D of Fig. 3. Extensive fiber pull-out can be seen in this microfractograph. It is interesting to point out that the portion CD indeed resembles the strain-softening characteristics of a damaged concrete specimen.

One interesting feature of the microfractographs shown in Fig. 6 is the periodic appearance of cracks along the fiber direction. This implies that crack density (which is defined as the number of cracks per unit length along the fiber direction) may play an important role in the tensile damage behavior of ceramic matrix composites.

Nicalon/CAS II specimens were also subjected to tensile loading at varying temperatures. Figure 7 shows the stress-strain curves at higher temperatures. It is seen that the strength of the composite decreases with increasing temperatures.

Figure 6. Tensile damage of the specimen at different stress levels.

Figure 7. Effects of temperatures on Nicalon/CAS II specimens.

spaced multiple transverse cracks are formed. When the crack spacing reaches a certain value, formation of new transverse cracks stops until failure. During this process debonding and possibly sliding at the fiber/matrix interface occurs. To capture this feature, our model consists of rows of periodic H-cracks in the composite (Fig. 8). Since the geometry is extremely complex the calculations are carried out using the Finite Element Technique. For this purpose a finite element program has been developed. The model geometry and FEM mesh are shown in Fig. 8. The strain energy release rates at the interface crack tip are calculated as the crack-tip nodes at the interface are released step by step. Then the total strain energy release rate G is computed as:

$$G = \frac{U_n - U_{n+1}}{t\Delta D} \quad (n=0,1,2, \dots)$$

where U_n is the strain energy associated with a particular crack length, t is the thickness of the specimen and ΔD is the crack length increment. When this value is greater than G_{cr} (critical strain energy release rate), then the crack propagates. Since it is extremely difficult to measure G_{cr} of interface, here we estimate G_{cr} by

4. THE THEORETICAL MODEL AND COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

As explained earlier, to predict and simulate the observed tensile behavior of ceramic matrix composites a theoretical model has been developed.

The model is based on observed behavior during tensile testing.

From experiments, it is known that, after the appearance of initial transverse matrix cracks, with increasing load regularly

Figure 8. Finite element model.

Figure 9. Typical stress vs. strain curves from FEM model.

Figure 10. Comparison of 3 tests and a FEM model

matching one point of the stress-strain curve with the calculated value. The stress-strain curves obtained from this model are shown in Fig 9 for two crack spacings namely $L/S=2.4$ and $L/S=4.8$. In Fig 10, the theoretical results obtained from this model for $L/S=2.4$ are compared with experimental data. The comparison indicates that, we have a very good match between experimental data and theoretical prediction.

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CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES: ANALYSIS
